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Employee performance factors in the Indonesian public sector social service

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Abstract

The City Social Service is an institution that engages and deals with social problems at the city level which is responsible for developing, improving quality and coordinating elements of social problems in the city scope. It is in this agency or institution that the employees of the City Social Service Office should work optimally for the advancement of service quality in overcoming social problems in society that still look complex. This research aims to study the impact of leadership on employee performance, which is mediated by the work motivation and work discipline of the Social Service Bureau of the "S" District, East Java Province, Indonesia. The data was collected through a survey of all employees of the "S" Regency of the East Java Social Welfare Office. The proposed model was tested using the Structural Equation Model (SEM). This research concludes proper leadership is needed and can direct work motivation towards improving employee performance. Leadership implemented by a leader is expected to be a supporter and lead to the achievement of maximum performance, that will be a sign of the existence of a leader in an agency / organization. With a different model of the relationship between variables, which is mediated by two variables (work motivation and work discipline) about leadership on employee performance, it is hoped that it can provide a broader picture, in this case what needs to be considered to improve employee performance. This research is one of the few researches that used two mediation methods to complement effect leadership on employee performance at Social Welfare Office. This research enriches information/theory regarding the relationship between employee performance factors in the public sector and offers a new approach to the relationship between variables.

Keywords: Employee performance; Leadership; Social services; Work discipline; Work motivation

1. Introduction

Employee performance is the result of the performance that someone or organization of humans in a corporation can acquire in phrases of excellent and amount in step with their respective authority, responsibilities, so one can attempt to acquire the dreams of the applicable corporation. The role of employees is critical to the success or failure of an organization. Employee performance is influenced by various factors. These factors are very important to pay attention to so that performance can be improved for the smooth running of a process of the organization. These factors are described below.

Work discipline is very important in employee performance. Employee discipline is very necessary for the smooth running of organizational programs. Every employee is expected to have a work disciplined attitude to follow the rules and carry out their duties properly. Organizations themselves can make policies that will affect employee discipline.

Work motivation is an impetus that arises from a person's encouragement to take action for a specific purpose, whether consciously or not. Of course, the work motivation of each employee is different.

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Employees who have a good performing leader will usually give a good performance as well. The way superiors lead their employees will greatly affect the performance of the organization and employees. The more complex problems that arise, it requires transformational leadership that is charismatic and visionary who is able to identify, provide, and promote employee trust. Describe complex problems and implement good managerial practices to improve the performance and success of any change effort [1].

In an organization governance, success or failure in carrying out their duties and governance, is influenced by leadership, through leadership and supported by organizational capacity adequate governance, then administration of good governance will come true, the opposite is leadership weakness is one of the causes of collapse the performance of the bureaucracy in Indonesia by Istianto in [2].

The social service is a government agency that plays a role in dealing with social problems that occur in the community. It is in this institution that it is expected that the activities of serving employees can play a role in the realization of the social model and be able to overcome all problems related to social problems in the community.

The City Social Service is an institution that engages and deals with social problems at the city level which is responsible for developing, improving quality and coordinating elements of social problems in the city scope. It is in this agency or institution that the employees of the City Social Service Office should work optimally for the advancement of service quality in overcoming social problems in society that still look complex.

The purpose of this research is to investigate the influence of leadership on employee performance mediated by work motivation and work discipline of the Department of Social Services in the "S" District of East Java, Indonesia. A new discussion here is to model between these four variables to find out the factors that influence the performance of employees in the social welfare sector. The outcomes of this research can be used as a reference and as a new topic in organizational behavioral research.

The structure of this article is as follows: The second part provides a literature review of this article. The third part discusses methods. The fourth part introduces data collection, data processing, and analysis of results and discussions. The fifth part summarizes the research results.

1.1. Literature Review

Service employee performance is the result of the quantity and quality of work performed by employees according to their assigned responsibilities [3]. Performance is the result of employees' work in terms of quality, quantity, working hours and cooperation to achieve the objectives established by the organization [4]. Performance is the level at which employees meet job requirements [5]. Performance is the work performance of employees [6]. From the various descriptions above, it can be concluded that employee performance is their performance relative to predetermined standards. Both the quantity and quality of work performance in the organization depend on the responsibilities assigned to him. Employee performance is strongly influenced by several factors, including: leadership, work motivation, work discipline, etc.

1.1.1. Leadership

According to [7] leadership is an ability that can influence a group to achieve goals. The leadership described by [8] is a process in which individuals influence others and inspire, encourage, motivate and guide their activities to help achieve the goals of the group or organization. [9] defines leadership as the ability to influence people who have the ability to achieve goals.

The function of leadership in an organization is defined as the ability to influence others in an effort to achieve organizational goals. In this context, it can be seen that the task of the leader is more related to issues of motivating, encouraging, and influencing subordinates to achieve organizational goals [10].

Leadership is the overall pattern of the leader's behavior, including the behavior of his subordinates. Leadership style describes a constant combination of philosophies, abilities, developments, and attitudes that form the basis of individual behavior. The activities and dynamics that occur within the company largely depend on the leader who leads the operation of the organization. The effectiveness of subordinates depends to a large extent on the leadership effectiveness of the leader [11]. The success of a leader depends on the leader's style or way of moving his subordinates through his attitudes and behaviors and the rules applicable to the organization he leads [12]. [13] pointed out that leadership is the art of influencing the behavior of others or influencing human behavior, whether it is an individual or a group.

The person who fulfils the responsibility of leadership is called a leader. According to [14] a leader is an individual who can influence the behavior of others without relying on violence. A leader is an individual who is accepted as a leader by others. They can also motivate others to develop, innovate, and create [15]. In order for the organization to function optimally, the manager must have leadership skills. Basically, leadership and management are two different things, but they have similarities and an inseparable relationship. In an organization, the leadership factor plays an important role because of that leadership which will drive and direct the organization within achieving goals, is a task that is not easy because have to understand each different behavior of subordinates. A leader must know very well the characteristic of the leader and on the equal time realize the factors of management as an influencing activity, the ability to invite, direct, create ideas. In order to achieve the planned organizational goals, the manager of the operational management must also be able to act as a leader. The role of the leader must be able play a role in an organization, leaders must be able to explore potentials that is in him and makes use of it within organizational unit. According to these definitions, it's far clear that leadership is a management feature intently related to the fulfilment of organizational dreams.

1.1.2. Work Motivation

According to [16] motivation is a system describe someone's strength, course and perseverance to gain its dreams. There are 3 major keys: strength, course and perseverance. Intensity describes how difficult someone is. High depth will now no longer convey the anticipated effects except efforts are dreams that gain the organization. Within other words, motivation must be directional. Hard work the direction of the organization's goals is the effort that must be cultivated. Finally, motivation Persistent. Motivation is something that encourages employees / members of the organization to support real action within realizing needs [10]. This is a measure of how long it takes one person can maintain his business. Individual is motivated people will continue to work to achieve their goals.

Work Motivation is the motivation to improve a person's morale, so he is willing to make every effort to obtain satisfaction [17]. This kind of work motivation is the motivation that encourages members of the organization to spend time on various activities. These activities are his responsibility and his obligation to achieve the previously set organizational goals [18]. High work motivation in a person is indicated by the emergence of a desire to obtain satisfactory work results in carrying out work, because with work motivation will try to get work performance, have responsibility in carrying out tasks and are always looking for new innovations [19].

Conclusions can be drawn. In other words, work motivation is a self-motivating effort do a good job and spread all the skills they have enable the company's goals to be achieved. If anyone has very motivated, then he will do. If someone is not motivated, it is the greatest, and vice versa. At work, he will not have new things to do achieve company goals.

This motivation is an important subject for leadership, because according to the definition the leader must work and through other people. Leaders need understand people behave in a certain order can influence it to work according to that the company wants.

1.1.3. Work Discipline

Discipline can be interpreted as written or unwritten behavior [20]. Work discipline may be described as an mindset recognize and obey the relevant regulations, each written and unwritten and are capable of deliver them out and now no longer keep away from to get hold of sanctions if he violates the obligations and government given to him [21].

Discipline is attitude or behavior describes adherence to a rules and conditions for its operation an orderly and orderly life. Having become one with him, then the attitude or action that is done no longer or not felt at all as a burden, even the opposite will be burdens himself when he is not do as usual. Values obedience has become a part of behavior in his life. Before others claim strange, uncomfortable or feeling ashamed and guilty when he did deviate [2].

According to [22] employee work discipline is a characteristic of employees who consciously obey certain organizational rules and regulations. According to [23], work discipline is a person's awareness and willingness to comply with all applicable company regulations and social norms.

Work discipline is a person's capacity to work regularly, diligently and work in keeping with relevant regulations without violating predetermined regulations [24]. Strengthening discipline is critical to the business enterprise due to the fact field carries policies that personnel have to follow. Through discipline, it is expected to make work more efficient. Work discipline can be seen as a big deal conducive to the interests of the organization and employee. For the organization, work discipline will ensure maintain order and perform duties smoothly in order to get the best results. At the same time, employees will get a pleasant working atmosphere Improve morale when performing work. Therefore, employees can perform their duties full of consciousness, can develop energy and thoughts achieve

organizational goals as much as possible. In paying attention to the role of humans in the organization, in order to achieve the specified goals, high discipline is needed so that it can achieve optimal work results or achieve the desired results together.

The relationship among variables can be described in the review below, employee performance can be influenced by the leadership of a leader. Most researchers state leadership have a significant effect on employee performance [25], [26], [27], [28], [29], [30], [31], [32], [33].

Employee performance can also be influenced significantly with work motivation as conveyed by these researchers [25], [26], [27], [29], [31], [33], [34], [35]. It is different from research by [28], [32] who state work motivation has no significant effect on employee performance.

Beside leadership and work motivation, employee performance can be influenced significantly by work discipline as the research result from [25], [26], [27], [28], [29], [31], [32], [34], [35]. Differ with research from [30] who state work discipline has no significant effect on employee performance.

2. Material and methods

The form of studies used on this study is a quantitative study. Quantitative studies is a studies approach primarily based totally at the wonderful idea this is used to take a look at a selected populace or sample, whilst for facts series the use of studies tools, facts evaluation is quantitative/statistical, with the reason of trying out predetermined hypotheses [36]. Population is a generalized area, composed of objects/themes with certain qualities and characteristics set by researchers to study and draw conclusions [36]. The population in this study is all social service employees of S' Regency in East Java Province, namely 43 employees. Although the sample size is less than 100, it is better overall, so the study is a population study [37], so the sample size is 43 employees.

According to [36] a variable is anything in any form that a researcher has determined to study it to obtain relevant information. The operation of variables in this study is defined as follows:

2.1. Leadership

Leadership is the inherent ability of a person to influence others or guide certain parties to achieve their goals. Organizations or institutions need leadership to work hard to achieve the goals of the organization. [13] pointed out that leadership is the art of influencing the behavior of others or influencing human behavior, whether it is an individual or a group. The leadership indicators are as follows (5 questions/indicators in the smartPLS 3 structural model)

- The ability to direct employees.
- Think strategically.
- Have good knowledge and personality.
- Individual attention.
- Have good communication skills.

2.2. Work Motivation

Work motivation for employees is a main thing that encourages someone to work. Work motivation for employees is carried out in order to direct the power and potential of employees to work productively. According to Maslow quoted by [23] work motivation indicators are (5 questions/indicators in smartPLS 3 structural model)

- Physical needs.
- Needs related to security.
- Social related needs.
- Appreciation needs.
- Needs for self-realization.

2.3. Work Discipline

Work discipline is the ability of a person to work regularly, continuously and in accordance with applicable rules without violating predetermined rules. According to [24], the indicators of work discipline are (3 questions/indicators in smartPLS 3 structural model)

- Employee obedience to predetermined regulations.
- Comply with the work procedures that have been determined.
- Carry out all the duties and obligations that have been determined.

2.4. Employee Performance

According to [38] performance is a measurement of the expected work results in the form of something optimal. Performance indicators according to Robbins is as follows (5 questions/indicators in smartPLS 3 structural model):

- Quality
- Quantity
- On time
- Independence
- Work commitment

The data collection method uses questionnaires. According to [37], the questionnaire is defined as the number of written questions used to obtain information from the interviewee about their personality or things they know. In this study, the questionnaire used is closed, where there are answers so that the respondent can directly choose the answers provided. This questionnaire method is useful for collecting data from respondents. Regarding respondent data, respondents' responses to research variables include: leadership, work motivation, work discipline, and performance. Measurement instruments used in this study used a Likert scale. With a Likert scale, the measured variables are translated into variable indicators. For each question item is given a score of 1 to 5, namely Strongly Agree (SS) - 5, Agree (S) - 4, Disagree less (KS) - 3, Disagree (TS) - 2, Strongly Disagree (STS) - 1. The analytical method used is the statistical method which is predicted to help in making choices to simply accept and reject the hypothesis. Data processing uses structural equation modelling (SEM) Smart PLS.

Source: processed figure with Smart PLS Remarks: Variable X = Leadership; Variable Z1= Work motivation' Variable Z2= Work discipline; Variable Y= Employee Performance

Figure 1 Research Model

2.5. Hypothesis

- H1: Leadership (X) has a direct and significant impact on employee performance (Y)
- H2: Leadership (X) has a direct and significant influence on work motivation (Z1)
- H3: Leadership (X) has a direct and significant effect on work discipline (Z2)
- H4: Work motivation (Z1) has a direct and significant impact on employee performance (Y)
- H5: Work discipline (Z2) has a direct and significant impact on employee performance (Y)

- H6: Leadership (X) has an indirect and significant influence on employee performance (Y) through work motivation (Z1)
- H7: Leadership (X) has an indirect and significant influence on employee performance (Y) through work discipline (Z2)

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Sample Evaluation of Measurement (Outer Model)

3.1.1. Validity Test

If the weight issue of the indicator on the expected variable is extra than 0.5, the indicator can be declared valid. The Smart PLS 3 output of the weight issue gives the following assessment results:

Table 1 Result for Outer Loading

Indicators	X	Y	Z1	Z2
D1				0.992
D2				0.875
D3				0.957
L1	0.966			
L2	0.919			
L3	0.945			
L4	0.730			
L5	0.950			
M1			0.679	
M2			0.933	
M3			0.885	
M4			0.859	
M5			0.914	
P1		0.939		
P2		0.926		
P3		0.966		
P4		0.717		
P5		0.929		

Source: processed field data with Smart PLS

The validity test of the mirrored image index makes use of the correlation among the object rating and the variable rating. If different signs of the identical variable extrude (or are eliminated from the model), the size with reflective signs will suggest the extrude in signs within side the variable. The above table indicates that the value furnished through the loading thing is better than the endorsed value of 0.5. The minimal value of the M1 indicator is 0.679. This method that the signs used on this take a look at may be declared as legitimate or have reached convergence validity. The following discern is the weight thing diagram of every indicator on this studies model:

Source: processed with Smart PLS

Figure 2 Value of Loading Factor

It is also necessary to test the discrimination effectiveness of the reflective index through cross-loading, as shown below:

Table 2 Result for Cross Loading

Indicators	X	Y	Z1	Z2
D1	0.357	0.511	0.270	0.992
D2	0.492	0.100	0.243	0.875
D3	0.221	0.504	0.130	0.957
L1	0.966	0.251	0.404	0.431
L2	0.919	-0.021	0.348	0.252
L3	0.945	0.016	0.281	0.315
L4	0.730	0.422	0.499	0.282
L5	0.950	0.015	0.338	0.303
M1	0.142	0.341	0.670	0.041
M2	0.404	0.258	0.933	0.192
M3	0.424	0.325	0.885	0.227
M4	0.330	0.506	0.859	0.304
M5	0.513	0.223	0.914	0.148
P1	0.232	0.939	0.368	0.410
P2	0.030	0.926	0.216	0.475
P3	0.253	0.966	0.418	0.422
P4	0.224	0.717	0.425	0.280
P5	0.136	0.929	0.299	0.287

Source: processed field data with Smart PLS

An indicator is said legitimate if the indicator's goal variable utilization is maximum as compared to different variables. The table above suggests that the burden component of the X indicator (L1 to L5) has a better load component for the

X variable than the alternative variables. For example, purposes, the burden component from L1 on X variable is more than the burden component for Y (0.251), Z1 (0.404), and Z2 (0.431). The equal applies to different signs. Therefore, the capacity settlement predicts the indicator for that block higher than the signs for different blocks. Another manner to test the effectiveness of the difference is to have a take a observe the rectangular root of the suggest variance extraction (AVE) value. The advocated value is more than 0.5. The AVE values for this examine are:

Table 3 Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

Variables	AVE
X	0.821
Y	0.810
Z1	0.738
Z2	0.889

Source: processed field data with Smart PLS

The table above shows AVE values higher than 0.5 for all variables included in the research model. The minimum AVE value for the Z1 variable (work motivation) is 0.738.

3.1.2. Reliability Test

Based The reliability test is performed by viewing the reliability value of the composite material from the indicator block of the measured variable. If the overall reliability result is higher than 0.7, a satisfactory value will be displayed. The following are the comprehensive reliability values:

Table 4 Composite Reliability

Variables	Composite Reliability
X	0.958
Y	0.955
Z1	0.933
Z2	0.960

Source: processed field data with Smart PLS

The table above shows that the overall confidence score for all variables is greater than 0.7. This indicates that all variables in the derived model meet the discriminant validity criteria. Minimum comprehensive confidence value for variable Z1 (work motivation) is 0.933. Cronbach’s Alpha can also enhance reliability testing, where the output of Smart PLS 3 can get the following results

Table 5 Cronbach’s Alpha

Variables	Cronbach’s Alpha
X	0.945
Y	0.938
Z1	0.909
Z2	0.937

Source: processed field data with Smart PLS

An The recommended value is above 0.6, and the above table shows that the Cronbach’s Alpha value of all variables is above 0.6. The minimum value of the variable Z1 (work motivation) is 0.909.

3.2. Structural Model Testing (Inner Model)

Once the estimated model satisfies the conditions of the external model, the next step is to test the structural model (internal model). Here is the R-squared value of this variable:

Table 6 R Square

Variables	R Square
Y	0.275
Z1	0.191
Z2	0.132

Source: processed field data with Smart PLS

The above table gives a value of 0.275 for the Y variable, which means that X, Z1, and Z2 can explain 27.5% of the Y variance. The value of the Z1 variable is 0.191, which means that X can explain 19.1% of the Z1 variance. The value of the Z2 variable is 0.132, which means that X can explain 13.2% of the Z2 variance.

3.2.1. Hypothesis testing is as follows:

Table 7 Path Coefficients

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
X → Y	-0.088	-0.154	0.250	0.354	0.724
X → Z1	0.438	0.445	0.169	2.593	0.010
X → Z2	0.363	0.407	0.178	2.037	0.042
Z1 → Y	0.339	0.348	0.171	1.988	0.047
Z2 → Y	0.380	0.472	0.225	1.690	0.092
X → Z1 → Y	0.149	0.151	0.106	1.406	0.160
X → Z2 → Y	0.138	0.220	0.193	0.714	0.475

Source: processed field data with Smart PLS

The final result of the hypothesis test is as follows:

Three Hypothesis are accepted

- X (Leadership) → Z1 (Work Motivation)
- X (Leadership) → Z2 (Work Discipline)
- Z1 (Work Motivation) → Y (Employee Performance)

Because the P value is <0.05, and all values are positive.

Four Hypothesis are rejected

- X (Leadership) → Y (Employee Performance)
- Z2 (Work Discipline) → Y (Employee Performance)
- X (Leadership) → Z1 (Work Motivation) → Y (Employee Performance)
- X (Leadership) → Z2 (Work Discipline) → Y (Employee Performance)

Because the P Values is > 0.05, and all values are positive (except X → Y).

According to the above test results, it can be considered that proper work motivation can have a direct and significant effect on achieving good employee performance, because undirected work motivation cannot be used as an intermediary to lead employee performance. Leadership itself only has a direct and significant impact on work

motivation. It requires the right leadership skills and can guide work motivation to improve employee performance. Similarly, leadership will only have a direct and significant impact on work discipline. Correct leadership is needed and can direct work discipline towards improving the performance of these employees. Due to general work discipline, just obeying the rules is not enough to encourage the achievement of good employee performance.

It is inappropriate if the leadership of an agency (regional government) cannot direct its subordinate employees to achieve optimal employee performance. Moreover, if the leadership is not strong enough, employees actually give positive results in improving employee performance. Leadership that is carried out by a leader is expected to be a supporter and lead to the achievement of maximum performance, it will be a sign of the existence of a leader in an agency / organization.

Of course, a suitable communication media is needed to bridge the communication process between leaders and subordinates in terms of improving performance. Correct management control and reporting system is needed so that leadership can drive work motivation and work discipline in the right direction for optimal performance achievement. It is undeniable that, especially in the reporting process, operational process reports and work results play an important role in enabling the organization to develop in a better direction. Without a good and integrated reporting system, it is difficult for senior leaders to make decisions, and it takes a long time to make strategic decisions for the organization. The performance reporting system must be able to show the level of participation of the lowest-level employees, which can show the ongoing review process and the improvements being made together [39].

Leadership ability in moving and empowering employees will affect performance. Lodge and Derek in [2] mentioned, behavior leaders have a significant impact attitude, behavior and performance employees. The effectiveness of the leader is affected subordinate characteristics and associated with the communication process that occurs between leaders and subordinates. Leaders are declared unsuccessful if they cannot motivate and satisfying employees at a job and certain environment. The job of the leader is encouraging subordinates to have competencies and opportunities to develop in anticipation of every challenge and opportunities at work.

3.3. Managerial Implication

In addition to providing input for organizations/companies, this research also provides input to enrich the theory of the relationship between employee performance factors in the public sector.

4. Conclusion

The results of this study are:

- Leadership (X) has an insignificant impact on employee performance (Y).
- Leadership (X) has a significant direct impact on work motivation (Z1).
- Leadership (X) has a significant direct impact on work discipline (Z2).
- Work motivation (Z1) has a significant direct impact on employee performance (Y).
- Work discipline (Z2) has an insignificant impact on employee performance (Y).
- Leadership (X) has an insignificant impact on employee performance (Y) through work motivation (Z1)
- Leadership (X) has an insignificant impact on employee performance (Y) through work discipline (Z2)

Correct leadership is needed and can direct work motivation towards improving employee performance. Leadership that is carried out by a leader is expected to be a supporter and lead to the achievement of maximum performance, it will be a sign of the existence of a leader in an agency / organization.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The Authors wish to declare that none has any interest to disclose.

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